

Screening of phytochemicals and estimation of secondary metabolites in plant species *Euphorbia prostrata* L. and *Euphorbia parviflora* L.

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ABSTRACT

Phytochemicals, typically secondary metabolites, such as alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, terpenoids and tannins are the active ingredients that give medicinal plants their therapeutic benefits. Parts of the medicinal plants *Euphorbia prostrata* and *E. parviflora* were examined for secondary metabolites. Each secondary metabolite was estimated using a different technique, such as the Folin-Ciocalteu method for phenol, the Folin-Denis method for tannin, and the aluminium chloride colorimetric method for flavonoids. The highest concentrations of phenol, tannin and flavonoids were found in *Euphorbia parviflora*. In contrast, *Euphorbia prostrata* had a reduced phenol concentration. Future research on secondary metabolites will require the use of strong analytical separation and detection methods such as GCMS and HR-LCMS.

Keywords: Phytochemicals, Folin-Denis, Alkaloids, Medicinal plants, Flavonoids.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary metabolites present in the plant tissues identified medicinal properties, including flavonoids, terpenoids and phenolic acids, exhibiting a spectrum of biological activities, including free radical scavenging (Aslam *et al.* 2024); they also exhibit protease inhibition, allelopathic, antibacterial, and antifungal effects (Abu-Romman *et al.*, 2010). Secondary metabolites, which act as plant defense mechanisms, are particularly effective against microbes and play a crucial role in the treatment of skin diseases (Parekh and Chanda, 2007).

In plants like *Euphorbia prostrata* and *Euphorbia parviflora*, many bioactive phytochemicals are present, which have been used in traditional medicines across various cultures for their alleged therapeutic effects, addressing conditions such as skin ailments, hemorrhagic disorders, and respiratory complications. (Salehi *et al.* 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The selected plant species were randomly collected from various districts of the Marathwada region.

Plant Extraction: Plant materials of *Euphorbia prostrata* and *E. parviflora* (50 g of each) were ground into a fine powder using an electronic blender. The powdered plant material was then subjected to Soxhlet extraction in the laboratory for effective extraction. The resulting crude extracts were used for quantitative estimation, and the filtrates were preserved for further analysis.

Phytochemical studies:

Tannin Content Determination: The tannin content of the plant samples was determined using the Folin-Denis method. (Ram and Malhotra, 1993; Sane, 2002)

Materials: Folin-Denis Reagent, Sodium Carbonate Solution, Standard Tannic Acid Solution, Working Standard Solution

Procedure: The extraction and quantification of tannin are performed by boiling 0.5 g of plant material, centrifuging, and reacting 1 ml of the extract with Folin-Denis reagent and sodium carbonate. The resulting blue color is measured at 700 nm and concentration is determined using a tannic acid standard curve.

Phenol Content Determination: Phenol content was measured using the method of Singleton and Rossi

(1965). catechol as the standard. Mix the sample and Folin reagent (1:1), incubate for 3 min, add 1 ml Na₂CO₃, dilute to 10 ml, and measure absorbance at 650 nm after 90 min in darkness.

Flavonoid Content Determination: Flavonoid content was determined using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. the Aluminum Chloride Colorimetric Assay for determining Total Flavonoid Content, where AlCl₃ forms a colored complex with flavonoids measured at 430 nm and quantified against a Rutin standard curve.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening of medicinal plant

Sr. No.	Plant species	Flavonoids	Phenols	Tannins
1	<i>Euphorbia prostrata</i> L.	+	+	+
2	<i>Euphorbia parviflora</i> L.	+	+	+

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical Analysis

Preliminary phytochemical screening of *Euphorbia prostrata* L. and *E. parviflora* L. revealed primary phytochemicals, viz., tannins, flavonoids, and phenols. Both fractions of the *Euphorbia* species contained phenolic compounds to varying extents. Among these fractions, *E. prostrata* exhibited the highest phenolic content, with an optical density at 760 nm corresponding to 1.896 mg/mL of catechol equivalent, while *E. parviflora* showed a phenolic content of 0.729 mg/mL of catechol equivalent.

Table 2: Estimations of Phenol, Tannins and Flavonoids

Standard Conc. Mg/ml	Phenol	Tannins	Flavonoids	
	O.D of Standard Solution at 760nm	O.D of Standard Solution at 500 nm	O.D of Standard Solution at 500 nm	O.D of Standard Solution at 500 nm
0.1	0.062	0.004	0.763	0.085
0.2	0.087	0.007	0.830	0.131
0.3	0.120	0.007	1.011	0.262
0.4	0.202	0.008	1.613	0.404
0.5	0.285	0.009	2.000	0.462
0.6	0.324	0.010	2.000	0.487
0.7	0.350	0.012	2.001	0.613
0.8	0.370	0.014	2.020	0.768
0.9	0.430	0.015	2.030	0.909
1.0	0.502	0.016	2.035	1.135

Sample	O.D at 730 nm	O.D at 500 nm	S.O. at 430 nm
<i>Euphorbia prostrata</i> L.	1.896	0.073	0.307
<i>Euphorbia parviflora</i> L.	0.729	0.026	0.117

O.D of Standard Solution at 760nm

O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm

O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm

Using the Folin-Denis method, the tannin content of the *Euphorbia* species was determined to be 0.073 and 0.026 mg/mL, expressed as tannic acid equivalents, and measured spectrophotometrically at 500 nm. The Folin-Denis reagent, a mixture of phosphotungstic and phosphomolybdic acids, forms a blue tungsten oxide when reduced by phenols (Snell and Snell, 1937). *E. prostrata* exhibited the highest tannin content, while *E. parviflora* contained the lowest.

Flavonoids were quantified using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. The flavonoid content of *E. prostrata* was higher than that of *E. parviflora*, with *E. prostrata* showing a content of 0.307 mg/mL, equivalent to 100 mg of rutin, while *E. parviflora* showed a lower flavonoid content of 0.117 mg/mL, equivalent to 100 mg of rutin, measured spectrophotometrically at 430 nm

CONCLUSION

The results indicated that the quantities of phenols, flavonoids, and tannins were present in varying concentrations in the selected *Euphorbia* species. Among them, *Euphorbia prostrata* exhibited the highest concentrations of all the phytochemicals evaluated. Future studies should focus on a more detailed analysis of secondary metabolites using advanced techniques such as Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) and High-Resolution Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (HR-LC-MS).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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